

COMPRESSION AND FLOWBACK IN POLYDISPERSE COMPOSITE GRANULAR PACKS

M. Kulkarni and O. Ochoa*

Mechanical Engineering, Texas A&M University, College Station, USA

* Ozden O. Ochoa (ochoa@tamu.edu)

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1 Introduction

Granular materials are a collection of individual solid particles large enough so that the physics of motion is independent of temperature. Their application areas range from geophysics, pharmacy, oil & gas, powder metallurgy, polymer technology, casting technology, agriculture, and construction industry [1]. Analytical characterization of granular packs are carried out with discrete element method (DEM) to obtain nonlinear stress-strain response, failure envelopes, transition from brittle to ductile behavior, hysteresis as well as identifying local failure and shear bands. In general, DEM formulation utilizes simplified contact relationships, neglects rotational stiffness and it is not conducive for large deformations in particles. These limitations can be alleviated with the explicit dynamic finite element method wherein each particle is represented with its own mesh to simulate multi-particle interactions accounting for changes in the particle geometry due to plastic deformation and damage [2].

Our objective is to understand the effects of particle material, shape and size in granular packs (proppants) enlisted in hydraulic fracturing treatments employed for oil/gas well simulation. Proppants are delivered to these fractures to ensure that the fluid flow paths remain open by resisting the rock pressure (closure stresses). The replacement of sand with a mixture of lightweight ground-nutshells, ceramic and metal particles has opened new research areas aimed at reducing the fracturing fluid viscosity enabling efficient particle placement while increasing the resistance to closure stresses [3, 4]. The effectiveness of a proppant pack is dependent on its ability to withstand closure stresses while maintaining a highly permeable pack with large void spaces, which ensure a high fluid flow rate.

2 Analysis

Herein we present models of the granular media with a combined finite/discrete element method employing ABAQUS explicit code. General contact capability is utilized to simulate inter-particle interaction [5]. The primary parameters of interest are stresses developed in the particles and the corresponding void spaces.

The proppant pack is analyzed under confined compression to reflect the state within the pack far away from the wellbore. Proppant flowback (out flow of the particles from a compressed pack) is also studied by adding a transverse load on the particles to simulate pressure gradient and fluid drag forces, while the particles continue to be subjected to compressive forces.

2.1 Particle Distributions and Pack Formation

The random number generation function in MATLAB is invoked to generate an initial random distribution of particles and sizes in a rectangular domain as shown in Figure 1a. The loose configuration mesh is created with the preprocessing software Altair Hypermesh [6].

The particles are considered as linear elastic and allowed to undergo a fall under gravitational loading in ABAQUS explicit 6.8.3. Three dimensional continuum elements, C3D8R, with eight nodes and reduced integration are used to model the particles and the rock platens. The spherical particles are represented as cylinders for simplicity. Plane strain conditions are enforced along the cylinder axis. The largest particles are composed of 1200 elements while the smallest particles are described with 150 elements. There are total of 32,265 elements with 71,332 nodes. The configuration at the end of the free fall (Figure 1b) is imported into a new analysis step where the particles are assigned their

appropriate material properties; elastic or elastic-plastic. This approach removes the need to monitor the plastic strains developed in particles during free fall.

2.2 Confined Compression Study

This model consists of 150 particles placed between the two horizontal rock platens that represent the fracture width (f_w) as shown in Figure 2. Two additional rigid platens are introduced as side enclosures. The distance between the two rigid platens represents the fracture length (f_l). The lower rock platen (B) is constrained against any motion and the compressive load is introduced through the rigid elements at the upper surface of the rock platen (A). The maximum value of the compressive load is 100 N, equivalent to 77 MPa closure stress.

The particle mixture is identified with weight percent of its composition; walnut (15%) and ceramic (85%). Gaussian distribution for particle radii is as follows; the walnut diameter range is from 0.8-1.2 mm while the ceramics vary between 0.35-0.55 mm. The specific gravity of ceramic and walnut is 3.6 and 1.25 respectively. Walnut is described with an elastic-plastic constitutive behavior obtained from single particle compression tests [7]. Ceramic is represented as a quasi-brittle material where it remains linear-elastic until the tensile stresses reach its bending strength. At this stage micro-cracking is assumed to occur and at subsequent increments, the modulus is represented as $E = (1-d)E_0$. E_0 is the undamaged elastic modulus and d is the scalar degradation variable, which is defined as a part of material strain softening data in the concrete damage plasticity model [5]. The rock platens are assigned linear elastic material properties of shale rock. The ratio of elastic moduli of ceramic to walnut and shale rock to walnut is 80:1 and 4:1 respectively.

The analysis is quasi-static with incremental compressive load. Mass scaling is employed to speed up the analysis. Inertia effects are monitored during the simulation to ensure that they are negligible.

2.3 Proppant Flowback Study

This model accommodates 200 particles, each 1mm in diameter, in the fracture width of 4.5 mm. The fracture length is modeled with 50 particles. The load is applied over two steps i) confined

compression load, to avoid spurious proppant production and ii) transverse load with simultaneous removal of one side enclosure, Fig. 3. The loading is incremental and quasi-static, and the confined compression stage is load controlled. The concentrated force is applied at the reference node of the rigid top layer of the rock platen. Note that the transverse force representing flowback is dependent both on the pressure gradient and the particle diameter. In this model the force is equivalent to 1.686 MPa/m (75 psi/ft).

The flowback resistance of a proppant pack is studied by observing the number and distance from the unconstrained end over which particles fall out of the pack and the formation of a stable arch. Two different packs are considered; first one has 15% walnut and 85% ceramic particles and the second one consists of 100% ceramic particles. Two models with coefficient of friction $\mu = 0$ and 0.3 are considered to study the influence of inter-particle friction. The effect of closure stress on the flowback is considered by comparing particle response at 50 MPa and 100 MPa pressure for both packs without inter-particle friction. Treating shale rock as linear elastic as well as elastic-plastic material address the influence of the rock.

3 Observations

3.1 Confined Compression

The effects of polydispersity on the pack response reveal the following observations. At the end of the free fall, particles are segregated where the larger particles tend to stay at the top of the pack as shown in Fig. 1b. This is in line with the findings for granular material segregation in the literature [1]. Compression response of the granular pack reveals that the harder ceramic particles carry most of the load which appears as stress chains in the von Mises stress contour plot in Fig. 4. The softer and larger walnut particles undergo significant plastic deformation but do not carry high loads as can be seen in Fig. 5.

The value of the damage variable for the ceramic particles indicating degradation in the element stiffness is presented in Fig. 6. In the current model a limited degradation approximately 15% of its original value for only a few elements is observed.

This is primarily due to the high co-ordination number of ceramic particles, which resists the development of tensile strains. Damage initiation is observed at the surface and at the center of the circular ceramic particles. The load vs. displacement response of the pack is nonlinear with gradual stiffening of the response.

At present, polydisperse models with 400 particles are being analyzed with a range of soft particle compositions, particle shapes and different inter-particle friction coefficients.

3.2 Flowback

The results show that friction, nonlinear material behavior, and high closure stresses significantly resist particle flowback. For the 15% walnut mixture with elastic-plastic rock at 50 MPa closure stress, the model with friction shows only a limited particle flowback compared to the model without friction as observed from Fig. 7a and 7b where the transverse nodal velocity contours are presented. This is attributed to the combined action of particle interlocking, inter-particle friction and particle embedment in the deformable rock. Note that only particle interlocking and embedment occur for the frictionless condition.

A stable arch indicating high flowback resistance is also observed in Fig. 7b. It can be concluded that a higher closure stress (100 MPa vs. 50 MPa) leads to reduced flowback as shown in Figs 7a and 7c. On the other hand the pack is highly compressed with low porosity and corresponding loss of fluid flow rate. The difference in shale rock material behavior that impacts particle embedment is illustrated in Fig. 7a and 7d for elastic-plastic and elastic rock at 50MPa closure stress. A softer more deformable rock better resists flowback by allowing a higher particle embedment, which resists transverse particle motion. The effect of pack composition on flowback can be observed by comparing Fig. 7c and 8 for the 15% walnut mixture and a 100% ceramic pack respectively. Softer particle mixture enhances flowback resistance but also results in significant loss of porosity.

Flowback is currently being introduced in the polydisperse models with a range of mixtures to identify an optimum particle mix.

4 Conclusions

Polydispersed proppant models are evaluated for compaction and flowback conditions. Numerical simulations of particle packing and different loading conditions provide valuable insight into the pack response. It is observed that soft particle mixtures, softer rocks and higher closure stresses resist proppant flowback but may tend to reduce porosity resulting in a loss of fluid flow rate. Further simulations that incorporate different pack compositions and particle shapes are necessary to better understand the mechanics governing both the individual particle and the pack behavior under combined loads to enable development of a parametric test bed and reduce the requirement of expensive testing.

Fig. 1a. Initial low density particle distribution

Fig. 1b. Configuration of particles at the end of free fall imported in a new analysis

Fig. 2. Schematic of confined compression

Fig. 3. Transverse load and particle flowback stage for the flowback model

Fig. 4. von Mises stress contour for polydispersed confined compression model at 70 MPa pressure

Fig. 5. Equivalent plastic strain contour for polydispersed confined compression model at 70 MPa pressure

Fig. 6. Contour for scalar damage variable in ceramic particles at 70 MPa pressure. Maximum value is 0.15.

Fig. 7a. Flowback for 15% walnut mixture, no friction, elastic-plastic rock and 50 MPa closure stress

Fig. 7b. Flowback for 15% walnut mixture with 0.3 coefficient of friction, elastic-plastic rock and 50 MPa closure stress

Fig. 7c. Flowback for 15% walnut mixture, no friction, elastic-plastic rock and 100 MPa closure stress

Fig. 7d. Flowback for 15% walnut mixture, no friction, linear-elastic rock and 50 MPa closure stress

Fig. 8. Flowback for 100% ceramic mixture, no friction, elastic-plastic rock and 100 MPa closure stress

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